

Apparent digestibility of different batch of *Hermetia illucens* meals for rainbow trout

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One of the aims of the H2020 SUSINCHAIN project is to evaluate the apparent digestibility coefficient (ADC) of four commercial black soldier fly (BSF) meals produced within one year, to highlight how fluctuation on the BSF meals composition could influence digestibility parameters in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*).

In vivo digestibility trial has been conducted following the procedure described by Bureau et al. (1992). Briefly, a high quality reference diet (REF) has been prepared, and four experimental diets were obtained by mixing REF and one of the BSF meals in a 70:30 ratio (as is basis) to produce: BSF1, BSF2, BSF3 and BSF4 diet. Celite[®] as inert marker (acid insoluble ash) has been included in REF diet to serve as inert digestion indicator. Fish were introduced in 250 L cylindroconical tanks (18 fish/tank), supplied by artesian well water (13 ± 1°C) in flow-through open system. Diets were randomly assigned to three replicate tank/diet. Fish were fed by hand, seven days/week, and faeces were collected twice a day from each tank for four consecutive weeks, using a continuous automatic device, as reported by Choubert et al. (1982). Faeces were collected, frozen (−20 °C) and then freeze-dried prior to subsequent chemical analyses.

The ADC for the nutrients and energy of the experimental and REF diets were calculated as follows (Bureau et al., 1999):

$$ADC = 1 - (F/D \times D_i/F_i)$$

Where: F = % nutrient (or KJ/g gross energy) of faeces; D = % nutrient (or KJ/g gross energy) of reference or experimental diet; D_i = % marker indicator of diet; F_i = % marker indicator of faeces. The ADCs of nutrients and energy for each of the tested insect meal (ingredient) were calculated as follows (Bureau et al., 1999):

$$ADC_{ing} = ADC_{test} + [(ADC_{test} - ADC_{ref}) \times ((0.7 \times D_{ref}) / (0.3 \times D_{ing}))]$$

Where: ADC test = ADC of the experimental diet; ADC ref = ADC of the reference diet; D ref = g 100g⁻¹ nutrient (or MJ kg⁻¹ gross energy) of the reference diet (DM basis); D ing = g 100g⁻¹ nutrient (or MJ kg⁻¹ gross energy) of the test ingredient (DM basis).